

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FORMULATION AND IN-VITRO EVALUATION OF BUCCAL
TABLETS OF ATENOLOL****Abdul Sayeed*, Ishrath Fatima, Syed Areefulla Hussainy and Faizan Sayeed**
MESCO College of Pharmacy, Mustaidpura, Karwan Road, Hyderabad.**Abstract:**

The aim of the study was to explore the drug delivery system of Atenolol for treatment of antihypertensive. A satisfactory attempt was made to develop buccal drug delivery system of Atenolol and evaluate it. Influence of the formulation variables on hardness, drug uniformity, mucoadhesive strength, drug release is evident. Formulation Af5 has successfully sustained the release of Atenolol in buccal cavity, with great mucoadhesive strength. The formulation Af5 showed good pre compression and post compression parameters and follows Zero order and Higuchi kinetics. After the Stability studies the optimized formulation doesn't show any remarkable change in drug release. Based on the all experiment results it can be concluded that Guar gum and sodium alginate containing buccal formulation would be the suitable candidate for mucoadhesive drug delivery of Atenolol with sustained release properties for the treatment of Antihypertensive.

Corresponding author:

Abdul Sayeed,
MESCO College of Pharmacy,
Mustaidpura, Karwan Road, Hyderabad.
Email: areefulla581@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Abdul Sayeed et al., *Formulation and in-vitro evaluation of buccal Tablets of atenolol.., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (11).*

INTRODUCTION:**BUCCAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM**

Drug delivery via membranes of the oral cavity can be subdivided as follows.

- Sublingual delivery, in which the administration of drug via the sublingual mucosa to the systemic circulation.¹
- Buccal delivery, in which the administration of drug via the buccal mucosa (the lining of cheek) to the systemic circulation via internal jugular vein.²
- Local delivery, for the treatment of conditions of the oral cavity, principally aphthous ulcers, fungal conditions and periodontal diseases by applications of the bioadhesive system either to the palate, or the cheek.³

These oral sites differ from each other, in terms of anatomy, permeability to an applied drug and their ability to retain a delivery system for desired period of time. The sublingual mucosa is relatively permeable, giving rapid absorption and acceptable bioavailability of many drugs and is convenient, accessible and generally well acceptable, which makes the oral mucosa. Finally the buccal site rather attractive for drug delivery.⁴

- Its ability to recover after local treatment is pronounced, and hence allowed a wide range of formulation to be used, e.g., bioadhesive ointment and patches.⁵
- The oral mucosa is accessible, so dosage forms can be administered and even removed from the site of application.⁶
- Since patients are well adapted to the oral administration of drugs in general, patient's acceptance and compliance is expected to be good.⁷
- According to its natural function the oral mucosa is routinely exposed to a multitude of different external compounds and, therefore, is supposed to be rather robust and less prone to irreversible irritation or damage by dosage form, it's drug, excipients or additive.

Local delivery of drug to tissue of the oral cavity has a number of applications including the treatment of toothache, periodontal diseases, dental carries, bacterial and fungal infections and aphthous stomatitis.⁸

Overview of the Oral Cavity⁹:

The different anatomical regions of the oral cavity and mucosal tissues are shown in Figure no.1. The various target sites for drug delivery and absorption may include the upper and lower lips, gums, hard palate, soft palate, floor of the mouth (sublingual), tongue, and buccal mucosal tissue (cheek). The oral mucosal tissues can be divided into two types, namely, keratinized epithelium of the masticatory regions consisting of the gums palatal mucosa, and the inner side of the lips and non-keratinized regions consisting of the floor of mouth (sublingual) and the buccal mucosa. The differences between the two types of epithelia are:

- The superficial layer of the non-keratinized layer is rougher when compared to keratinized epithelium and
- The elongated rate processes, which provide the attachment of epithelium to the underlying connective tissue, are deeper and narrower in keratinized epithelium as opposed to non keratinized epithelium.³

The oral mucosa is composed of an outermost layer of stratified squamous epithelium¹⁰. Below this lies a basement membrane, a lamina propria followed by the sub mucosa as the innermost layer. The epithelium is similar to stratified squamous epithelia found in the rest of the body in that it has a mitotically active basal cell layer, advancing through a number of differentiating intermediate layers to the superficial layers, where cells are shed from the surface of the epithelium.¹¹

Fig. 1: Anatomic regions of oral cavity

Aim and Objective: The aim of the present investigation is to develop and characterize sustained release buccoadhesive tablets of Atenolol.

- The buccal route was chosen because of its good accessibility, robustness of the epithelium, facile removal of the dosage form, relatively low enzymatic activity, and natural clearance mechanism for elimination of the drug from buccal area, satisfactory patient compliance and avoidance of first pass hepatic metabolism
- The route provides intimate contact between dosage form and absorbing tissue thereby resulting in high drug concentration in a local area and hence high drug flux through the absorbing tissue and drugs showing poor and unpredictable absorption from the stomach and intestine can be administered via the oral mucosa.

So an attempt has made to formulate Atenolol as the buccal tablet. As the drug is directed through buccal region, drug reaches into systemic circulation directly

METHODOLOGY:

Analytical Methods

Calibration Curve of Atenolol

Procedure

Preparation of standard solution:

Weigh accurately 100 mg of Atenolol was dissolved in 100 ml of volumetric flask using dissolution medium (phosphate buffer) which gives concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Then 1ml of stock solution was taken and diluted to 100 ml which gives a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Preparation of working standard solutions: from this stock solution subsequent dilutions were made in phosphate buffer ph 6.8 in order to get 2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 8 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, Absorbance of these solutions were measured at λ max 226nm using UV-Visible spectrophotometer and standard curve was plotted. The linearity plot was obtained for the aliquot concentration of 2, 4, 6, 8; 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with the absorbance was seen at 226nm.

Formulation of Mucoadhesive Tablets of Atenolol:

Preparation

In this work, direct compression method has been employed to prepare buccal tablet with HPMC and Guar gum as polymers because with the dry granulation the hardness of tablets has increased because of which rate of drug release got decreased. For one tablet accurately weighed 300 mg was used in the formulation.

Procedure: All the ingredients were accurately weighed and passed through mesh # 60. In order to mix all ingredients thoroughly Drug, polymers, micro crystalline cellulose, Aspartame were blended geometrically in mortar and pestle for 10 minutes then magnesium stearate were mixed for 1-2 min.

The powder blends of various proportions were evaluated for angle of repose, Carr's compressibility index and compressed into tablets of diameter 9mm on Cadmach press16 Station machine. Using stainless steel flat surface dies and punches by maintaining individual tablet weight constant at 300 mg.

Table No 1: Composition of Atenolol Buccal Tablets

Ingredients(mg)	Af1	Af2	Af3	Af4	Af5	Af6
Atenolol	100	100	100	100	100	100
Hydroxyl propyl methyl cellulose	30	45	60	--	--	--
Guar gum	--	--	--	30	45	60
Acacia	15	15	15	15	15	15
Sodium alginate	15	30	45	15	30	45
Microcrystalline cellulose	131.5	101.5	71.5	131.5	101.5	71.5
Aspartame	1	1	1	1	1	1
Magnesium stearate	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5
Total weight	300	300	300	300	300	300

Characterization of Tablets:

Thickness:

The thickness of the tablets was measured by vernier calipers. It is expressed in **mm**.

Hardness:

Tablets require a certain amount of strength or hardness and resistance to friability, to withstand mechanical shocks of handling in manufacture, packing and shipping. The hardness of tablet was measured by Monsanto hardness tester. The tablets from each batch were used for hardness studies and results are expressed in **Kg/cm²**.

Weight variation test:

Ten tablets were selected at randomly from the lot and weighed individually to check for weight variation.

Friability:

It was performed in Roche friabilator where the tablets were subjected to the combined effect of abrasion and shock by utilizing a plastic chamber that revolves at 25 rpm dropping the tablets at a distance of six inches with each revolution. Pre weighted samples of 20 tablets were placed in the Friabilator, which is then operated for 100 revolutions. The tablets are then dusted and reweighed. Conventional compressed tablets that loose less than 0.5 to 1 % of

their weight are generally considered acceptable.

% Friability= (initial weight-final weight/initial weight) x100

Determination of Drug content

Twenty tablets were taken and triturated well. The quantity equivalent to 100mg of atenolol was dissolved in 100ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8 Solution on rotary shaker overnight. The solution was centrifuged and supernatant was collected. The absorbance was measured using UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 226nm.

Swelling Index

The swelling properties of the tablets were evaluated by determination of percent of swelling. Each tablet was weighed (W1) and placed in petri dish with 5ml of PB P^H6.8 and incubated at 37⁰c for predetermined times. After placing the formulation for specified time, the tablets were wiped off to remove excess of surface water by using filter paper and weighed (W2).

In- vitro drug release study

To examine the release mechanism of atenolol from the prepared buccoadhesive tablets, the results were analyzed according to the following equation:

$$M_t = k.t^n$$

$$M_\infty$$

Where M_t/M_∞ is the fractional drug released at time t , k is a kinetic constant incorporating structural and geometrical characteristics of drug / polymer system [device], and n is the diffusion exponent that characterizes the mechanism of drug release. It is known that for non-swelling tablets, drug release can generally be expressed by the Fickian diffusion mechanism, for which $n=0.5$, whereas for most erodible matrices, a zero order release rate kinetics is followed, for which $n = 1$. For non-fickian release, the n value falls between 0.5 and 1.0 ($0.5 < n < 0.89$) whereas in the case super case II transport $n > 0.89$.

Data of the in-vitro release was fit in to different equations and kinetic models to explain the release kinetics of atenolol from buccal tablets.

Stability studies

Stability studies were performed at a temperature of $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $65 \pm 5\% \text{RH}$ and $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $75 \pm 5\% \text{RH}$, over a period of three months (90 days) for the optimized buccal tablet. Sufficient number of tablets were packed in amber colored screw capped bottles and kept in stability chamber maintained at $40 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ & $75\% \text{RH}$. Samples were taken at monthly intervals for drug content estimation. At the end of three

months period, dissolution test and drug content studies were performed to determine the drug release profiles and drug content.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Standard Graph of Atenolol

Preparation of standard solution:

Weigh accurately 100 mg of Atenolol was dissolved in 100 ml of volumetric flask using dissolution medium (phosphate buffer) which gives concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Then 1ml of stock solution was taken and diluted to 100 ml which gives a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Preparation of working standard solutions:

from this stock solution subsequent dilutions were made in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 in order to get 2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 8 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, Absorbance of these solutions were measured at λ max 226nm using UV-Visible spectrophotometer and standard curve was plotted. The linearity plot was obtained for the aliquot concentration of 2, 4, 6, 8; 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with the absorbance was seen at 226nm.

The standard graph of Atenolol has shown good linearity with R^2 values 0.998 in pH 6.8 buffer, which suggests that it obeys the "Beer-Lambert's law".

Table No.2 : Standard Graph of Atenolol

Conc. (mcg/mL)	Absorbance
	6.8 pH Buffer
0	0
2	0.091 \pm 0.01
4	0.182 \pm 0.05
6	0.264 \pm 0.07
8	0.346 \pm 0.04
10	0.422 \pm 0.06

10 mg pure drug was dissolved in methanol and was diluted to give concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and was scanned between 200 nm and 400 nm for the determination of λ . The wavelength of 226 nm was selected as for λ_{max} . The same was used for further analysis of drug solution and absorbance of final standard solution was measured at 226 nm.

Table No.3: FTIR Spectra of Atenolol formulation

Characteristic peak	Observed range	Pure drug	Optimized formulation
OH	3700-3200	3366.80	3488.91
N-H	3000-2800	2854.61	2942.33
C-O	1310-1250	1243.43	1304.51

FTIR studies were performed to understand the compatibilities between the drug with different excipients. The figures above illustrate that the functional groups like O-H Stretching with the observation range of 3700-3200 has peaks at 3366.80 in pure drug, 3488.91 drug and excipient. Similarly the functional group N-H Stretching has a peak range of 3000-2800 has peaks at 2854.61 in pure drug, 2942.33 drug and excipient. Similarly the functional group C-O strong Stretching has a peak range of 1310-1250 has peaks at 1243.43 in pure drug, 1304.51 drug and excipient.

Characterization of Blend:

The blends for Bucoadhesive tablets were characterized with respect to angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, and Hausner's ratio. Angle of repose was less than 30° and Carr's index values were less than 15 for the blend of all the batches indicating excellent to good flowability and compressibility. Hausner's ratio was less than 1.11 for all the batches indicating excellent flow properties.

Table No.4: Physical Properties of Pre-compression Blend

Formulations	Angle of repose (°)	Bulk Density (g/mL)	Tapped Density (g/mL)	Carr's Index (%)	Hausner's ratio	Flow property
Af1	29.25 ⁰	0.34	0.38	10.52	1.11	Good
Af2	27.40 ⁰	0.35	0.41	14.63	1.17	Good
Af3	22.87 ⁰	0.30	0.33	9.09	1.01	Excellent
Af4	22.45 ⁰	0.31	0.34	8.82	1.09	Excellent
Af5	24.37 ⁰	0.44	0.49	10.20	1.11	Good
Af6	28.41 ⁰	0.32	0.35	8.57	1.09	Excellent

The results of the uniformity of weight, hardness, thickness, friability, and drug content of the tablets are given in Table. All the tablets of different batches complied with the official requirements of uniformity of weight as their weights varied between 298.2±0.22 and 300.2±0.48mg. The hardness of the tablets ranged from 5.04±0.57 to 5.42±0.31 kg/cm² and the friability values were less than 0.5% indicating that the Bucoadhesive tablets were compact and hard. The thickness of the tablets ranged from 2.52±0.17 to 2.65±0.66 mm. All the formulations satisfied the content of the drug as they contained 98 to 101 % of atenolol and good uniformity in drug content was observed. Thus all the physical attributes of the prepared tablets were found to be practically within control.

Table No. 5: Physical Evaluation of Bucoadhesive Tablets

F.Code	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Thickness (mm)	Weight (mg)	Friability (%)	Drug content (%)
Af1	5.20 ±0.44	2.52±0.17	300.2±0.48	0.38	98.21±0.37
Af2	5.42±0.31	2.57±0.25	299.4±0.54	0.40	99.42±0.80
Af3	5.12±0.40	2.54±0.80	298.6±0.41	0.44	99.17±0.47
Af4	5.26±0.55	2.50±0.20	298.8±0.64	0.52	100.22±0.15
Af5	5.04±0.57	2.65±0.66	300.6±0.14	0.50	100.24±0.42
Af6	5.19±0.30	2.63±0.25	298.2±0.22	0.56	99.42±0.81

Swelling Index**Table No. 6 : Results of Percent swelling Index**

F. CODE	swelling Index
Af1	150
Af2	140
Af3	165
Af4	120
Af5	170
Af6	180

The swelling behavior of a buccal adhesive system is an important properties uniform and prolonged release and effective mucoadhesion. The swelling index study indicated that the rate of swelling was directly proportional to Sodium alginate and polymer content. Swelling index was calculated with respect to time. The swelling index gives an indication of the relative moisture absorption capacities of polymers and whether the formulations maintain their integrity after moisture absorption. The results of present formulation were tabulated in the above table.

Mucoadhesion Time**Table No.7: Effects of Polymers on Mucoadhesion Time**

Formulation Code	Mucoadhesion Time
Af1	6
Af2	8
Af3	9
Af4	5
Af5	7
Af6	>9

Ex vivo residence time was determined by using sheep buccal mucosa. The mucoadhesion time is important to know how long the tablet could able to stick to the buccal mucosa. This adhesion time relates to the release rate of drug. The mucoadhesion time is as follows Af6> Af3> Af2> Af5> Af4> Af1. The bioadhesive tablet is important for good mucoadhesion. Bioadhesion characteristics are affected by the type and ratios of bioadhesive polymers. The results were tabulated in the above table.

In-vitro drug release study**Table No.8: In-Vitro Release of Formulation Af1- Af6**

Time	Af1	Af2	Af3	Af4	Af5	Af6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	17.6	20.6	7.2	21.03	9.8	14.6
2	39.8	31.5	16.25	34.25	17.24	25.12
3	54.31	42.6	26.49	48.15	28.15	33.64
4	70.61	54.1	37.18	62.41	45.62	46.24
5	86.29	68.7	55.41	78.36	62.18	56.19
6	94.21	85.9	68.12	93.6	75.26	68.35
7	--	94.6	79.35	--	89.17	74.29
8	--	--	86.47	--	96.28	84.26

Fig. 2: In-Vitro drug release for Formulation Af1-Af6

In-vitro drug release study

The *In-vitro* drug release study has been done for various formulations (Af1-Af6). The different ratios of polymers were used. The results shown that as the proportion of polymers in the formulation increases, cumulative percent drug released was found to be reduced. Among the six batches, formulation Af1 and Af4 have released 94.21% and 93.6% drug release in 6th hr respectively, F2 shows drug release of 94.6%. Whereas Af3, Af6 shows 86.47%, 84.26% drug release in 8th hr respectively, Af6 shows 96.28% drug release respectively. Among all formulations Af5 was optimized based on sustained drug release and highest drug release at 96.8% at 8th hr.

Kinetic Order Drug Release:

Table No.9 : Drug Release Kinetics for Optimized Formula Af5

	ZERO	FIRST	HIGUCHI	PEPPAS
	% CDR Vs T	Log % Remain Vs T	%CDR Vs \sqrt{T}	Log C Vs Log T
Slope	12.8871196	-0.1632458	36.889828	1.6822761
Intercept	-4.4750757	2.2134954	-19.740215	0.5775412
R 2	0.9895711	0.8523088	0.8725026	0.8285791

Drug release kinetics

In-vitro drug release data of all the buccal tablet formulations was subjected to goodness of fit test by linear regression analysis according to Zero order, first order, Higuchi's and Korsmeyer-Peppas models to ascertain the mechanism of drug release.

From the above data, it can be seen the formulation, Af5 have displayed zero order release kinetics (r^2 value of 0.989). From Peppas data, it is evident that the drug is released by nonFickian diffusion mechanism. This is because as the proportion of polymers in the matrix increased there was an increase in the amount of water uptake and proportionally greater swelling leading to a thicker gel layer. Zero-order release from swellable hydrophilic matrices occurs as a result of constant diffusional path lengths.

STABILITY STUDIES:

Table No.10 : Stability studies of Atenolol bucoadhesive tablet (Af5) at room temperature

Time	Colour	Assay		Cumulative % drug release		Surface pH	
		25±2 ⁰ c and 65±5%RH	40±2 ⁰ c and 75±5%RH	25±2 ⁰ c and 65±5%RH	40±2 ⁰ c and 75±5%RH	25±2 ⁰ c and 65±5%RH	40±2 ⁰ c and 75±5%RH
First day	White	100.24	100.24	96.28	96.28	6.6	6.6
30 days	White	100.22	100.18	96.19	96.11	6.6	6.6
60 days	White	100.01	99.48	95.84	95.45	6.6	6.6
90 days	White	99.54	99.12	95.12	94.84	6.6	6.6

Results from stability studies indicate that the formulated Atenolol bucoadhesive tablet are stable for a period of 3 months under 2 different conditions at 25±2⁰c and 65±5%RH and 40±2⁰c and 75±5%RH. There were no remarkable changes were observed during the period of storage.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that Atenolol can certainly be administered through the oral mucosa. The designed bucoadhesive tablets can overcome the disadvantage of extensive first pass effect and low oral bioavailability of Atenolol. This increased and predictable availability of Atenolol from designed formulation may result in substantial dose reduction of the dosage form when the drug is administered through oral mucosa so that it will be economical to the patient. Further work is recommended to support its efficacy claims by pharmacokinetic and

pharmacodynamic studies in human beings.

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